

**THE LARGEST (k, ℓ) -SUM-FREE SETS
IN COMPACT ABELIAN GROUPS**

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Abstract

A subset A of a finite abelian group is called (k, ℓ) -sum-free if $kA \cap \ell A = \emptyset$. In this paper, we extend this concept to compact abelian groups and study the question of determining the maximum size of a measurable (k, ℓ) -sum-free set. For integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and a compact abelian group G , let

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \sup\{\mu(A) : kA \cap \ell A = \emptyset\}$$

be the maximum possible size of a (k, ℓ) -sum-free subset of G . We prove that if $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$, where \mathbb{I} is the identity component of G , then

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \max\{\lambda_{k,\ell}(M), \lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I})\};$$

moreover, $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I}) = \frac{1}{k+\ell}$ if \mathbb{I} is nontrivial. We also discuss how this problem motivates a new framework for studying (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets in finite groups.

1. Introduction

The *Minkowski sum* of two subsets A and B of an additive abelian group G is

$$A + B = \{a + b : a \in A, b \in B\}.$$

When G is finite, a natural problem is determining the maximum size of a subset $A \subset G$ that is *sum-free*, i.e., satisfies $(A + A) \cap A = \emptyset$. In other words, A is sum-free if $x + y = z$ has no solution in A . Early progress on this problem for cyclic groups appears in the work of Diananda and Yap [4] and Wallis, Street, and Wallis [15]. In 2005, Green and Ruzsa [6] completely resolved this problem for finite abelian groups. Let $\lambda_{1,2}(G)$ denote the maximum density of a sum-free subset of G .

Theorem 1 (Green and Ruzsa [6]). *For any finite abelian group G with exponent $\exp(G)$, we have*

$$\lambda_{1,2}(G) = \max_{d|\exp(G)} \left\{ \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{3} \right\rceil \cdot \frac{1}{d} \right\}.$$

In particular, $\frac{2}{7} \leq \lambda_{1,2}(G) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, and both of these extremal values are achieved.

Other statistics on sum-free sets have been the object of considerable study (see [5, 14] and the references therein).

This problem has more recently been generalized to (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets. For a positive integer k , let $kA = \underbrace{A + \cdots + A}_k$ denote the k -fold Minkowski sum of A with itself (not to be confused with the k -fold dilation of A). Then, for a finite abelian group G , let

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \max \left\{ \frac{|A|}{|G|} : kA \cap \ell A = \emptyset \right\}$$

denote the maximum density of a (k, ℓ) -sum-free subset of G . Trivially, $\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = 0$ when $k = \ell$, so by convention we take $1 \leq k < \ell$.

Most work has focused on (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets in cyclic groups; the general abelian case remains far from understood. Important results are due to Bier and Chin [3] and Hamidoune and Plagne [7], whose approaches relied on Vosper’s Theorem and Kneser’s Theorem. In 2018, Bajnok and Matzke [2] found a general expression for $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ by analyzing (k, ℓ) -sum-free arithmetic progressions.

Theorem 2 (Bajnok and Matzke [2]). *For any integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{Z}_n) = \max_{d|n} \left\{ \left\lfloor \frac{d - \delta_d + r_d}{k + \ell} \right\rfloor \cdot \frac{1}{d} \right\},$$

where $\delta_d = \gcd(d, \ell - k)$ and r_d is the remainder of $k \left\lfloor \frac{d - \delta_d}{k + \ell} \right\rfloor$ modulo δ_d .

For further background, see the excellent exposition in [1].

One might wonder about the analogous problem on the circle group $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z}$ and the d -dimensional torus \mathbb{T}^d . In this paper, we generalize the study of (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets to compact abelian groups. (We take all of our compact groups to be Hausdorff.) This transition from the discrete setting to the continuous setting has a number of precedents in additive combinatorics; previous fruitful generalizations include analogs of Mann’s Theorem [9] and Freiman’s Theorem [11, 12]. Our generalization of sum-free sets, however, is new.

For a compact abelian group G , let μ be the probability Haar measure (normalized so that $\mu(G) = 1$). We then define

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \sup \{ \mu(A) : kA \cap \ell A = \emptyset \},$$

where the supremum runs over all measurable subsets $A \subset G$. Note that when G is finite, this definition coincides with the definition above.

We let \mathbb{I} denote the identity component of G (the connected component of G which contains the identity element). It is well known (see, e.g., [8], Theorem 5.4) that \mathbb{I} is a closed normal subgroup; the quotient $M = G/\mathbb{I}$ is the (topological) group of components of G . It can be shown that G is isomorphic (as a topological group)

to the Cartesian product $\mathbb{I} \times M$ when \mathbb{I} is an open set, which is the case that we consider in this paper.¹

The main result of this paper is the following formula for $\lambda_{k,\ell}(G)$ when G can be written as $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$ (as above).

Theorem 3. *For any integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and any compact abelian group $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$, we have*

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \max \{ \lambda_{k,\ell}(M), \lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I}) \}.$$

If \mathbb{I} is nontrivial, then we also have $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I}) = \frac{1}{k+\ell}$ and hence

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \max \left\{ \lambda_{k,\ell}(M), \frac{1}{k+\ell} \right\}.$$

Note that positive-dimensional compact abelian Lie groups are included in the latter case. In particular, $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{T}^d) = \frac{1}{k+\ell}$ answers our original question about the d -dimensional torus. We also remark that when \mathbb{I} is trivial (consists of only a single point), we have $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I}) = 0$ and $\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \lambda_{k,\ell}(M)$, as expected.

In Section 2, we prove Theorem 3. We will make use of the following deep classical result of Kneser [10]. Here, μ_* denotes the inner Haar probability measure. (Even on \mathbb{T} , the Minkowski sum of two measurable sets need not be measurable.)

Theorem 4 (Kneser [10]). *Let G be a compact abelian group with Haar probability measure μ , and let A and B be nonempty measurable subsets of G . Then*

$$\mu_*(A + B) \geq \min\{\mu(A) + \mu(B), 1\},$$

unless the stabilizer $H = \text{Stab}(A + B)$ is an open subgroup of G , in which case

$$\mu_*(A + B) \geq \mu(A) + \mu(B) - \mu(H).$$

In Section 3, we discuss some consequences of our results and possible future lines of inquiry. In particular, the compact case inspires a curious new framework for investigating (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets in the finite context.

2. Proofs

We begin by recording a few general observations.

¹If \mathbb{I} is open, then M is finite (since G is compact) and has the discrete topology (since \mathbb{I} is open). Index the connected components of G according to the corresponding elements of M . Write $M = \mathbb{Z}_{a_1} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z}_{a_r}$, where each \mathbb{Z}_{a_i} has generator m_i . For each m_i , choose an arbitrary element x_i in the corresponding connected component of G , and consider $a_i x_i$. Since connected compact abelian groups are divisible ([8], Theorem 24.25), there is an element $y_i \in \mathbb{I}$ such that $a_i y_i = a_i x_i$; then $z_i = x_i - y_i$ is an element with order a_i in the connected component of G corresponding to m_i . The subgroup of G generated by z_1, \dots, z_r is a closed and normal subgroup isomorphic to M . Since this subgroup intersects \mathbb{I} only at the identity element of G , we conclude (see, e.g., [13], page 343) that G is isomorphic (as a topological group) to $\mathbb{I} \times M$.

Lemma 1. *Let A and B be (not necessarily measurable) subsets of a compact abelian group G . If $\mu_*(A) + \mu_*(B) > 1$, then $A + B = G$.*

Proof. There exist closed subsets $A_* \subseteq A$ and $B_* \subseteq B$ satisfying $\mu(A_*) + \mu(B_*) > 1$. Assume (for the sake of contradiction) that there exists some $g \in G \setminus (A + B)$. Then $g \notin A_* + B_*$, so A_* and $\{g\} - B_*$ are disjoint. But $1 \geq \mu(A_*) + \mu(\{g\} - B_*) = \mu(A_*) + \mu(B_*)$ yields a contradiction. \square

Lemma 2. *Let $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$ be a compact abelian group. Then any open subgroup H of G is of the form $H = \mathbb{I} \times N$, where N is a subgroup of M .*

Proof. The set $U = \mathbb{I} \cap H$ is open in \mathbb{I} and nonempty (since it contains the identity of G). Then U and its cosets are an open partition of \mathbb{I} . Since \mathbb{I} is connected, $U = \mathbb{I}$. Finally, noting that H/\mathbb{I} is a subgroup of $G/\mathbb{I} \cong M$ completes the proof. \square

Lemma 3. *Let A be a nonempty subset of an abelian group G . Then for any integers $1 \leq i < j$, we have $\text{Stab}(iA) \subseteq \text{Stab}(jA)$ as an inclusion of subgroups.*

Proof. For any $h \in \text{Stab}(iA)$, we have $\{h\} + jA = (\{h\} + iA) + (j - i)A = iA + (j - i)A = jA$, so $h \in \text{Stab}(jA)$. \square

This is, of course, a specific instance of the general fact that $\text{Stab}(A)$ is a subgroup of $\text{Stab}(A + B)$ for any A, B . We now bound $\lambda_{k,\ell}(G)$ from above.

Theorem 5. *For any integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and any compact abelian group $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$, we have*

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) \leq \max \left\{ \lambda_{k,\ell}(M), \frac{1}{k + \ell} \right\}.$$

Proof. Assume (for the sake of contradiction) that there exists a (k, ℓ) -sum-free set $A \subseteq G$ with measure strictly greater than both $\lambda_{k,\ell}(M)$ and $\frac{1}{k + \ell}$. Let $H = \text{Stab}(\ell A)$. We consider two cases depending on whether or not H contains \mathbb{I} .

First, suppose H does not contain \mathbb{I} . Lemma 3 implies that \mathbb{I} is not contained in any $\text{Stab}(iA)$ for $2 \leq i \leq \ell$, so we conclude from Lemma 2 that these stabilizers are not open subgroups of G . Iterative applications of Theorem 4 then give $\mu_*(kA) \geq \min\{k\mu(A), 1\}$ and $\mu_*(\ell(-A)) = \mu_*(\ell A) \geq \min\{\ell\mu(A), 1\}$. Since

$$\mu_*(kA) + \mu_*(\ell A) > \frac{k}{k + \ell} + \frac{\ell}{k + \ell} = 1,$$

Lemma 1 tells us that $kA + \ell(-A) = G$, and, in particular, $0 \in kA + \ell(-A)$. So there exist $a_1, \dots, a_{k+\ell} \in A$ satisfying $a_1 + \dots + a_k = a_{k+1} + \dots + a_{k+\ell}$, which contradicts A being (k, ℓ) -sum-free.

Second, suppose H contains \mathbb{I} . This implies that ℓA is a union of cosets of \mathbb{I} : if $g \in (m + \mathbb{I}) \cap (\ell A)$, then $\mathbb{I} + \{g\} = m + \mathbb{I} \subseteq H + (\ell A) = \ell A$. Let

$$P = \{p \in M : (p + \mathbb{I}) \cap A \neq \emptyset\}$$

be the set of the elements of M whose corresponding components in G have nonempty intersection with A . Since $\frac{|P|}{|M|} \geq \mu(A) > \lambda_{k,\ell}(M)$, we have $kP \cap \ell P \neq \emptyset$. Then there exist $p_1, \dots, p_{k+\ell} \in P$ and $m \in M$ such that

$$p_1 + \dots + p_k = p_{k+1} + \dots + p_{k+\ell} = m.$$

So there also exist $a_1, \dots, a_{k+\ell} \in A$ with each $a_i \in p_i + \mathbb{I}$. Then

$$a_{k+1} + \dots + a_{k+\ell} \in (m + \mathbb{I}) \cap (\ell A),$$

whence we conclude that $m + \mathbb{I} \subseteq \ell A$. Finally,

$$a_1 + \dots + a_k \in (m + \mathbb{I}) \cap (kA) \subseteq (\ell A)$$

contradicts A being (k, ℓ) -sum-free. This completes the proof. □

Next, we establish lower bounds by constructing large (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets. The following lemma generalizes a common tool in the study of (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets in finite groups.

Lemma 4. *Fix any positive integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and any compact abelian group G . If G admits a surjective measurable homomorphism ϕ onto the compact abelian group H , then $\lambda_{k,\ell}(H) \leq \lambda_{k,\ell}(G)$.*

Proof. Let $S \subset H$ be a (k, ℓ) -sum-free set of density μ . Then $A = \phi^{-1}(S) \subset G$ is a (k, ℓ) -sum-free set ($\phi(kA)$ and $\phi(\ell A)$ are disjoint in H) with the same density (corresponding probability Haar measure). □

Lower bounds now follow from the obvious choices for H .

Lemma 5. *For any positive integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and any compact abelian group $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$, we have*

$$\max \{ \lambda_{k,\ell}(M), \lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I}) \} \leq \lambda_{k,\ell}(G).$$

Proof. Apply Lemma 4 with $H = M$ and $H = \mathbb{I}$. □

When \mathbb{I} is nontrivial, we can bound $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I})$ from below using Pontryagin duality.

Lemma 6. *For any positive integers $1 \leq k < \ell$ and any nontrivial compact connected abelian group G , we have*

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) \geq \frac{1}{k + \ell}.$$

Proof. Consider the Pontryagin dual \hat{G} (the group of characters of G). It is known (see, e.g., [8], Theorem 24.25) that a compact abelian group is connected if and only if its Pontryagin dual is torsion-free. Thus, \hat{G} is torsion-free, and it is nontrivial since G is nontrivial. Let $\chi \in \hat{G}$ be an element of infinite order. Since $\chi(G)$ is closed and dense in \mathbb{T} , we conclude that $\chi(G) = \mathbb{T}$. By Lemma 4, we have $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{T}) \leq \lambda_{k,\ell}(G)$. Finally, note that the set

$$S = \left(\frac{k}{\ell^2 - k^2}, \frac{\ell}{\ell^2 - k^2} \right) \subset \mathbb{T}$$

is a (k, ℓ) -sum-free set with measure $\frac{1}{k+\ell}$: the intervals $kS = \left(\frac{k^2}{\ell^2 - k^2}, \frac{k\ell}{\ell^2 - k^2} \right)$ and $\ell S = \left(\frac{k\ell}{\ell^2 - k^2}, \frac{\ell^2}{\ell^2 - k^2} \right)$ are disjoint in \mathbb{T} . □

At last, we show how these results imply Theorem 3.

Proof of Theorem 3. We condition on whether or not \mathbb{I} is trivial. If \mathbb{I} is trivial, then $\lambda_{k,\ell}(\mathbb{I}) = 0$ and G is isomorphic to M . In this case, the first statement of the theorem holds trivially. If \mathbb{I} is nontrivial, then it suffices to observe that the upper bound of Theorem 5 coincides with the lower bound of Lemma 5 (by Lemma 6). □

3. Discussion

Theorem 3 completely determines $\lambda_{k,\ell}(G)$ in terms of the largest possible (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets of its “connected” and “discrete” parts when the identity component of G is open. In the finite case (cf. Theorem 2), one must take into consideration the largest (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets in all subgroups; our Theorem 3 shows that for compact $G = \mathbb{I} \times M$, it suffices to look for (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets in only \mathbb{I} and M .

There remain many interesting questions in the case where the identity component of G is not open. Profinite groups (totally disconnected compact groups) are a particularly natural avenue for further inquiry. Consider, for instance, the case where G is the direct product of countably many finite cyclic groups:

$$G = (\mathbb{Z}_2)^{e_2} \times (\mathbb{Z}_3)^{e_3} \times (\mathbb{Z}_4)^{e_4} \times \dots$$

(with the e_i ’s either finite or ∞). Roughly speaking, the measurable subsets of M can be approximated by subsets of the form $S \times (G/H)$, where H is a finite subgroup of G and $S \subseteq H$. Then we expect $\lambda_{k,\ell}(G) = \sup\{\lambda_{k,\ell}(H)\}$, where H ranges over the finite subgroups of G . As a starting point, Theorem 2 provides lower bounds. When $k = 1$ and $\ell = 2$, we can also apply Theorem 1: for example, $\lambda_{1,2}((\mathbb{Z}_p)^\infty) = \lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \rceil \cdot \frac{1}{p}$.

The problem of finding (k, ℓ) -sum-free subsets when \mathbb{I} is a d -dimensional torus and M is finite motivates a set of related questions for finite abelian groups. Consider the maps ϕ_n taking subsets of \mathbb{T} to subsets of \mathbb{Z}_n via

$$A \mapsto \left\{ i \in \mathbb{Z}_n : \left(\frac{i}{n}, \frac{i+1}{n} \right) \subseteq A \right\}.$$

The fact $\left(\frac{i}{n}, \frac{i+1}{n} \right) + \left(\frac{j}{n}, \frac{j+1}{n} \right) = \left(\frac{i+j}{n}, \frac{i+j+2}{n} \right)$ implies that for any sets $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{T}$,

$$\{0, 1\} + \phi_n(A) + \phi_n(B) \subseteq \phi_n(A + B),$$

with equality when (but not only when) A and B are the unions of open intervals of the form $\left(\frac{i}{n}, \frac{i+1}{n} \right)$. We remark that any open sets can be arbitrarily well approximated from the inside in this manner for large enough n . This observation motivates the following set of definitions.

Let A, B , and C be subsets of a finite abelian group G . For lack of better notation, let $A *_C B = C + A + B$ be a “modified” sumset of A and B , and let

$$k *_C A = \underbrace{A *_C \cdots *_C A}_k = kA + (k - 1)C$$

be the k -fold iteration of this sumset. We can investigate (k, ℓ) -sum-free sets under this operation (i.e., with respect to fixed C) by defining

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}^C(G) = \max \left\{ \frac{|A|}{|G|} : (k *_C A) \cap (\ell *_C A) = \emptyset \right\}.$$

Of course, $\lambda_{k,\ell}^{\{0\}}(G) = \lambda_{k,\ell}(G)$ recovers the ordinary definition of the maximum size of a (k, ℓ) -sum-free set.

When $G = \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $C = \{0, 1\}$, we see that $\lambda_{k,\ell}^{\{0,1\}}(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ reflects the problem of finding open (k, ℓ) -sum-free subsets of \mathbb{T} . Theorem 3 for $G = \mathbb{T}$ gives

$$\lambda_{k,\ell}^{\{0,1\}}(\mathbb{Z}_n) \leq \frac{1}{k + \ell}.$$

(This bound also follows from Kneser’s Theorem for finite groups.) Note that equality is achieved at least whenever n is a multiple of $\ell^2 - k^2$ (Lemma 6). This group invariant seems an interesting object of study.

Question 1. *What can we say about $\lambda_{k,\ell}^{\{0,1\}}(\mathbb{Z}_n)$? Which values of n satisfy $\lambda_{k,\ell}^{\{0,1\}}(\mathbb{Z}_n) = \frac{1}{k+\ell}$? For fixed $1 \leq k < \ell$, which n minimizes $\lambda_{k,\ell}^{\{0,1\}}(\mathbb{Z}_n)$?*

Other compact abelian groups of the form $\mathbb{T}^d \times M$ (with M finite) analogously give rise to the more general problem of computing $\lambda_{k,\ell}^C(G)$ with $G = \mathbb{Z}_{n_1} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{Z}_{n_d} \times M$ and $C = \{(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_d, 0) : \varepsilon_i \in \{0, 1\}\}$. Finally, we propose that other choices of

C could lead to questions of future interest. (Zhang [16] has recently investigated some of these questions.)

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